

Finally its identity was established as rhazine by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir) with an authentic sample. The complete ^1H nmr assignment of rhazine, which to our knowledge has not been reported so far is given here. 200 MHz ^1H nmr (recorded in CDCl_3 on a Bruker WP-200) δ 1.66 (3H, dd, J 6.7 and 1.9 Hz, C(18)H); 1.70-2.05 (3H, br m, C(14)H₂ and OH); 2.70 (1H, ddd, J 13, 4.3 and 1.9 Hz, C(15)H); 2.95 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 3.31 (1H, dd, J 15.5 and 1.6 Hz, C(6)H); 3.00-3.12 (2H, m, C(5)H and C(6)H); 3.60-3.62 (2H, br, CH₂OH); 3.69 and 3.84 (AB-system each of 1H, d, J 10.5 Hz, N-C(21)H₂); 4.31 (1H, dd, J 10.4 and 0.8 Hz, C(3)H); 5.41 (1H, br q, J 6.7 Hz, C(19)H); 7.06 (1H, dt, J_o 7.0, J_m 1.5 Hz, C(10)H); 7.13 (1H, dt, J_o 7.0, J_m 1.5 Hz, C(11)H); 7.30 (1H, br dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, partially obscured by CHCl_3 signal, C(12)H); 7.44 (1H, br dd, J_o 8.6, J_m 1.5 Hz, C(9)H) and 7.98 (1H, br s, NH).

The concentrate of the benzene eluate afforded a non-alkaloidal compound, m.p. 184-85°, as white granules. It showed characteristic bands at 3 300-3 500 (br) for hydroxyl group in the ir spectrum. The spectroscopical data (uv, ir, ms) indicated that the compound was an aliphatic diol, C₂₈H₃₄O₂ (M^+ 426). A number of other alkaloidal components have been isolated. These are being characterised.

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Reference

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A New Flavonol Glycoside from the Mature Tubers of *Cyperus rotundus* L.

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WE have previously reported¹ a new saponin from mature tubers of *Cyperus rotundus* L. We now report the isolation of a flavonol glycoside (1)

C₂₈H₃₄O₁₆, m.p. 196° d from the same source. This glycoside has not been isolated earlier from any plant source.

1 on acid hydrolysis gave an aglycone and rhamnose. The aglycone C₁₆H₁₂O₇, m.p. 284° gave all characteristic colour reactions of a flavonol² and was identified as rhamnetin on the basis of uv, ir, nmr and mass fragmentation pattern and con-chromatography with an authentic sample.

Methylation of 1 followed by acid hydrolysis gave 5,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyquercetin confirming the attachment of sugar at 3-position. The glycoside was fully methylated, hydrolysed and the resulting partially methylated sugars were identified as 2,3-di-O-methylrhamnose and 2,3,4-tri-O-methylrhamnose^{3,4}. This established the glycoside as a (1→4) trioside of rhamnose linked at 3-position of the aglycone. On this basis, 1 was identified as rhamnetin 3-O-rhamnosyl (1→4) rhamnopyranoside.

Experimental

The tubers of *Cyperus rotundus* L. were extracted with ethanol, concentrated and extracted with ether and ethyl acetate, respectively. Extraction with ethyl acetate and chromatography over silica gel with C₆H₆-EtOAc (1:1) gave 1, m.p. 196° d (EtOH); λ_{max} (EtOH) 255 and 355; (AlCl₃) 260 and 400; (AlCl₃-HCl) 270 and 400; (NaOAc) 255; (NaOAc/H₃BO₃) 260 and 390 nm.

On hydrolysis, 1 gave rhamnetin and rhamnose (pc in EtOAc-pyridine-H₂O, 12:5:4 and EtOAc-PrOH-H₂O, 3:1:1). Methylation and acid hydrolysis gave 5,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyquercetin, identified by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample. 1 was methylated with Me₂SO₄ in aqueous NaOH and the methylated glycoside hydrolysed with 4N H₂SO₄. The partially methylated sugars were identified by pc (BuOH-EtOH-H₂O, 5:1:4).

References

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